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**RESEARCH ON
EXPORT LOGISTICS
OF AGRICULTURAL
PRODUCTS IN
UKRAINE DURING
MARTIAL LAW AND
ENSURING FOOD
SECURITY**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7798978>

Abstract

Ensuring food security is affected by the saturation of agricultural products produced domestically and imported. The military actions in Ukraine have negatively affected the export logistics of Ukrainian agricultural products to third countries, thus posing a threat to food security. The aim of the study is to diversify the export logistics of Ukrainian agricultural products as a result of the blockade of seaports by using the capabilities of railway and vehicle transports, cross-border cooperation between Ukraine and the European Union countries. The study is based on an assessment of the volume of exports of Ukrainian agricultural products, an analysis of the geographical structure of logistics exports, and the border crossing of Ukrainian agricultural products by different types of transport. The paper describes diversified logistics routes for exporting Ukrainian agricultural products. Based on research results, identifies promising directions of support for the

export logistics of Ukrainian agricultural products during martial law and ensuring food security.

Keywords: *agricultural products, logistics, export, food security, diversification.*

Introduction

Ukraine has a significant potential for agricultural production – it has large amounts of agricultural land, fixed assets used in crop and livestock production, production technologies, etc. Ukraine's agriculture sector is home to both large agro-industrial companies and small farms. Ukraine's agricultural production fully meets the needs of the domestic market and contributes to global food security. Ukraine is a major exporter of agricultural products to global markets. Actively contribute to this export logistics, represented by various types of grain transportation, and the formation of efficient logistics chains in cooperation with agricultural producers, transport companies, wholesale intermediaries, etc.

However, the hostilities and the blockade of seaports in southern Ukraine affected the entire logistics chain of agricultural exports and threatened food security in some countries. Most countries of the world were not prepared for this scenario. World leaders and governments are trying to solve the problems of export logistics of agricultural products by offering various support and assistance programmes, using various logistics routes and technical potential of transportation in their own countries. It should be noted that this problem has identified the need for further in-depth scientific research in this area and has formed a number of practical tasks to address this complex issue.

We have conducted a study of financial losses of Ukraine's agricultural exports during martial law (Bezartochnyi, Britchenko, & Bezartochna, 2022), but the constant recording of grain theft and export outside the country, destruction and damage to grain crops requires clarification of statistical information and its adjustment. The literature includes studies of ensuring the functioning of the food system and the agricultural sector of Ukraine in the current crisis conditions (Gadzalo, Ibatullin, & Luzan, 2022; Rusan, 2022); providing state support to the agricultural sector of the economy in wartime (Galanets, 2022). Research in the pre-war period was aimed

at ensuring the efficiency of grain logistics and the development of transport infrastructure (Kachurovskiy & Macyuk, 2019; Krysiuk, Moskvichenko, & Bulgaru, 2017; Moskvichenko, Stadnik, & Pavlenko, 2021; Potapova, Ushkalenko, & Kachurovskiy, 2018), etc.

The aim of the study is to diversify promising logistics routes for the export of Ukrainian agricultural products to ensuring food security. The main objectives of the study are: to determine the commodity structure of Ukrainian agricultural exports, to study the geographical structure of Ukrainian agricultural exports, the volume of transportation by various types of transport, to determine diversified logistics chains for the export of Ukrainian agricultural products, the conditions for liberalisation of logistics exports and customs procedures for agricultural products of Ukrainian agricultural enterprises.

Materials and Methods

The methodological basis of the study is the general economic principles and methods of a systematic approach to studying the process of export logistics of agricultural products from Ukraine during martial law and ensuring food security. The methods of analysis and synthesis were applied, which allowed identifying problems and determining directions to ensuring food security through the diversification of export logistics of agricultural products from Ukraine during martial law. Sources of statistical information on the agricultural sector were used, as well as the commodity and geographical structure of Ukrainian agricultural exports, and the volume of transportations by various types of transport was estimated. The abstract-logical method is used to diversifying the export logistics of agricultural products from Ukraine and ensuring food security.

Results and Discussion

Efficient export logistics is achieved by combining the possibilities of transporting goods by various types of transport and optimising logistics costs. This can be achieved through a well-established transport network, participants in the logistics process, increasing quality of transport infrastructure, intergovernmental agreements and appropriate government support. Violation of these

components in the export logistics system reduces the quality of services, timely receipt of goods by contractors, and increases the cost of transportation.

The hostilities have disrupted all supply chains within the country and caused an imbalance in export logistics. This has also affected the supply of agricultural products and created problems for global food security.

During martial law, the volume of agricultural exports from Ukraine decreased significantly (Table 6.1). The figure shows that in 2022-2023 MY compared to previous years, the export of agricultural products from Ukraine decreased by half as a result of military operations. In the commodity structure of Ukraine’s agricultural exports, the largest decline in exports was observed for rye and barley.

Table 6.1

Exports of agricultural products from Ukraine, 2020-2021 – 2022-2023 MYs, thousand tonnes

Agricultural products	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2022-2023 to (%)	
				2020-2021	2021-2022
Cereals and legumes, total	43939	48508	22746	51.8	46.9
• wheat	16413	18741	8411	51.2	44.9
• barley	4210	5752	1626	38.6	28.3
• rye	15.8	161.5	12.5	79.1	7.7
• corn	22596	23535	12624	55.9	53.6
Wheat flour	123.7	69.4	65.6	53.0	94.5
Other flour	1.1	1.5	3.4	309.1	226.7
Total flour	124.8	70.9	69.0	55.3	97.3
Total export (grain + flour)	44105	48579	22815	51.7	47.0

Source: based on data of State Customs Service of Ukraine

The geographical structure of exports certain types of agricultural products from Ukraine is shown in Figures 6.3-6.6.

Figure 6.3 shows that the largest importers of Ukrainian wheat in 2022-2023 MY are Turkey, Romania and Spain. The volumes of Ukrainian wheat exports to these countries increased during martial law. In 2022-2023 MY Romania became the intermediary country for Ukrainian wheat exports to the Black Sea seaports. Exports of

Ukrainian wheat to Indonesia, Bangladesh, Egypt and Lebanon decreased. A significant volume of Ukrainian wheat exports was achieved through cross-border trade with Hungary.

Figure 6.3 Geographical structure of Ukrainian wheat exports, July-December 2021-2022 – 2022-2023, thousand tonnes

Source: based on the data of the State Statistic Service of Ukraine and Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine

According to Figure 6.4, in 2022-2023 MY the largest export volumes of Ukrainian corn were to Romania, China, Spain, Poland and Hungary. The export of Ukrainian corn to Romania and Poland increased several times due to the diversification of logistics channels. Exports of Ukrainian corn to Turkey, the Netherlands and Egypt decreased.

Figure 6.5 shows that Romania and Spain are the largest importers of Ukrainian barley in 2022-2023 MY. The export volumes of Ukrainian barley decreased to Turkey, China, Libya and Lebanon during martial law. Romania and Poland, which have access to the Black and Baltic Seas, will become the diversified export channels for Ukrainian barley in 2022-2023 MY.

According to Figure 6.6, in 2022-2023 MY the exports of Ukrainian sunflower oil to the EU and Turkey decreased. The exports of Ukrainian sunflower oil to India, China and the UK increased.

Figure 6.4 Geographical structure of Ukrainian corn exports, July-December 2021-2022 – 2022-2023, thousand tonnes

Source: based on the data of the State Statistic Service of Ukraine and Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine

Figure 6.5 Geographical structure of Ukrainian barley exports, July-December 2021-2022 – 2022-2023, thousand tonnes

Source: based on the data of the State Statistic Service of Ukraine and Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine

Figure 6.6 Geographical structure of Ukrainian sunflower oil exports, July-December 2021-2022 – 2022-2023, thousand tonnes

Source: based on the data of the State Statistic Service of Ukraine and Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine

In general, due to Ukraine’s cross-border cooperation with EU countries (Poland, Romania, Hungary), agricultural exporters managed to ensure the logistics of certain types of products (wheat, barley, corn) to sea and land routes as transit to other countries and to ensuring food security.

The border crossing of Ukrainian agricultural products by type of transport is shown in Figure 6.7 The figure shows that during the study period, corn accounted for the largest share in the commodity structure of agricultural products (42.8%). By type of transport, the majority of agricultural products were transported through seaports (69.4%), despite their blockade and military operations in the south of the country. Railway and vehicle transports have become an alternative to logistical exports of Ukrainian agricultural products.

The vast majority of EU countries that share borders with Ukraine have responded positively to the establishment of alternative logistics routes for exporting Ukrainian agricultural products to third countries by railway and vehicle transports, and have eased conditions for freight clearance and customs procedures. In particular, liberal

conditions were introduced for the export of grain crops from Ukraine: Poland, the Baltic States, Slovakia, Hungary, Romania, Italy, Turkey, Bulgaria, Georgia, Denmark, Greece, and Austria. For example, Poland is speeding up border procedures and logistics of grain crops from Ukraine, while the G7 countries are forming new logistics chains for grain exports. Slovakia and Austria have lifted restrictions on the transportation of grain crops from Ukraine through their territory without any permits, which has allowed for unimpeded supply of agricultural products to seaports in Italy.

Figure 6.7 Border crossing of Ukrainian agricultural products by type of transport, March 2022 – March 2023, tonnes

Source: based on the data of the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine

To facilitate the export logistics and transit of Ukrainian agricultural products, the EU has exempted transporters from phytosanitary requirements (An action plan for EU-Ukraine Solidarity Lanes, 2022).

Table 6.2 shows the characteristics of logistics routes for Ukrainian agricultural exports.

Table 6.2

Logistics routes for exporting Ukrainian agricultural products through EU countries during martial law

Country	Characteristics
Slovakia	<p>In Slovakia, grain crops were transported from Ukraine by railway to the ferry in Bratislava and then by the Danube to the Romanian Black Sea port of Constanta, and then to Africa. This logistics route is shorter, cheaper, and more environmentally friendly.</p> <p>Slovakia has an effective logistics potential – it has established logistics chains with the European railway, vehicle and ferry network. The port of Bratislava is located in the middle of the Rhine-Main-Danube waterway. The railway network has sufficient capacity to increase traffic volumes in the south-north and east-west directions.</p>
Poland	<p>Poland has a 400-kilometre railway connecting Ukraine with Silesia.</p> <p>Poland and Ukraine have agreed to establish a joint freight company and simplify border regulations. Obstacles to the development of logistics routes for grain exports and increased transportation volumes include congestion in Polish seaports to the Baltic States, and an urgent need to increase wagons and build transport infrastructure.</p>
Romania	<p>The Romanian logistics route for grain exports from Ukraine is via railway, vehicle, ports and the Danube River. It is one of the priority routes and has prospects for further development. Romania is implementing measures to increase the transportation of grain crops from Ukraine through its territory, using national mechanisms to provide direct support. The logistics hub for Ukrainian grain exports in Romania is the seaport of Constanta, which is an alternative logistics route bypassing the seaports blocked in Ukraine. Grain crops are then transported to third countries.</p>
Lithuania	<p>Lithuania uses the Klaipeda port on the Baltic Sea and the Polish railway to transit grain crops from Ukraine to third countries. It takes a long time to ship products from Ukraine to Lithuania.</p>

Source: authors' generalisation

Table 6.2 shows that during martial law, four main logistics routes for exporting Ukrainian agricultural products to third countries to ensuring food security have been formed. It should be noted that despite the joint efforts of Ukraine and the EU countries to establish alternative logistics routes for the transportation of agricultural products, there are problems that complicate the transit of agricultural products. In particular, there is a lack of truck drivers, different railway gauges in Ukraine and the EU, overloading of customs infrastructure – seaports in Romania and Poland, lack of qualified personnel, etc.

In order to eliminate obstacles and problems in the export logistics of Ukrainian agricultural products and ensuring food security, the European Commission, together with the Member States, has created “solidarity routes”. Within these routes, it is proposed to implement a number of priority measures in the short term, namely (European Commission to establish Solidarity Lanes, 2022):

- Additional freight rolling stock, vessels and lorries: The Commission calls on EU market players to urgently make additional vehicles available. In order to match demand and supply and establish the relevant contacts, the Commission will set up a matchmaking logistics platform and ask Member States to designate dedicated Solidarity Lanes contact points (a “one-stop-shop”).

- Capacity of transport networks and transshipment terminals: Ukrainian agricultural export shipments should be prioritised, and infrastructure managers should make rail slots available for these exports. The Commission also calls on market players to urgently transfer mobile grain loaders to the relevant border terminals to speed up transshipment. A road transport agreement with Ukraine will also remove bottlenecks. To encourage EU transport operators to allow their vehicles to enter Ukraine, the Commission will also investigate options for top-up financial guarantees.

- Customs operations and other inspections: The Commission urges national authorities to apply maximum flexibility and to ensure adequate staffing to accelerate procedures at border crossing points.

- Storage of goods on the territory of the EU: The Commission will assess available storage capacity in the EU and coordinate with Member States to help secure more capacity for temporary storage of

Ukrainian exports.

In the medium and long term, the Commission will also work to increase the capacity of the infrastructure of new export corridors and to create new infrastructure links as part of Ukraine's recovery.

Conclusions

The blockade of part of Ukraine's territory and seaports by the enemy has disrupted the export logistics of agricultural products to third countries. During martial law, the country is activating its own potential and using untapped reserves to ensuring food security.

The study found that corn accounts for the largest volume of Ukrainian agricultural exports. As a result of the blockade of seaports, countries such as Poland, Lithuania and Romania have provided diversified logistics channels for the export of Ukrainian agrarian products to their ports in the Baltic and Black Seas. Despite the decline in exports of Ukrainian agrarian products by port, it still accounts for the largest share in the structure of transportation by types of transport.

Real support from countries around the world helped to establish alternative logistics chains for exporting agricultural products abroad. The cancellation of a number of formal procedures for exporting Ukrainian agricultural products through the EU countries and the establishment of close cooperation with potential neighbouring countries allowed for the optimisation of the transportation process, using vehicle, railway, port and ferry transports for export and transit. The develop and implementation of daily effective measures to increase logistics routes to ensuring the export of Ukrainian agricultural products and the development of transport infrastructure in the EU countries has helped to ensuring the promotion of agricultural products and food security.

By coordinating efforts between the countries and achieving victory in the war against the enemy, Ukraine will restore its agricultural export potential to pre-war levels and enhance synergies within the framework of joint cooperation in creating efficient export logistics chains and developing transport infrastructure. And this, in turn, will ensuring food security both within the country and in other countries.

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